

Film Viewing Habits of Postgraduate Students in Shivaji University, Kolhapur

Dr. Shivaji Jadhav

Coordinator, Department of Mass Communication,
Shivaji University, Kolhapur (Maharashtra, India)

Abstract:- This research explores the film viewing habits of postgraduate students at Shivaji University, Kolhapur by focusing on their film viewing habits and how their academic commitments along with personal preferences shape their consumption patterns. PG students are a unique demographic and their time is often consumed by doing assignments, research projects, and the pursuit of specialized knowledge. In between all of these obligations, watching movies and consuming other media could provide individuals with a social or intellectual activity in addition to a way for relaxation. This group's film-watching habits can provide important insights into how they manage the responsibilities of their studies with their interests and leisure time. Understanding PG students' film viewing habits can provide important insights into their leisure activities and stress-reduction methods, in the light of the expanding demands on their time and the growing value of cinema as both entertainment and educational content. Nowadays films occupy a significant portion of the media products consumed by people. At the same time, the question of the effectiveness of films' impact remains an open question in psychological science. Postgraduate students' attitudes towards elderly people improved after watching the film, while undergraduate students' negative views worsened. These contrasting effects can be attributed to individual differences such as age, educational level, and prior experiences with elderly people, and pre-existing attitudes. This suggests that personal factors mediate the film's impact. However, the positive changes observed immediately after viewing were not sustained over time, indicating that a single movie session does not produce lasting effects on attitudes. Further research is needed to understand how to achieve long-term changes.

Keywords:- Film Viewing Patterns, Student Habits, Entertainment Preferences, Academic Pressure.

I. INTRODUCTION

Film viewing habits refer to the patterns and preferences individuals or groups have when watching movies. This can include factors like the frequency of viewing, preferred genres, the choice of viewing platform such as theaters, streaming services, or DVDs. It is also about the social context in which films are watched either alone or with family and friends. These habits can be influenced by various factors such as cultural background,

technological advancements, and personal preferences. Understanding these habits can provide insights into broader trends in entertainment consumption. Film viewing habits include the types of films watched, how often people watch films, that is, the viewing frequency, the viewing context, the platforms used to watch films such as streaming services namely, Netflix, Amazon Prime or other TV channels. It also includes choices regarding what to watch, including factors like director, actors, or film ratings. Additionally, when people prefer to watch films, that is, the time of viewing, the social influence and the emotional or situational factors of how mood or specific situations influence film choices. All these habits can vary greatly among different groups based on age, culture, educational fields and other demographic factors. 'Different movies have different impacts on society. Comic, adventures, biographical, and fantasy movies provide a positive impact. Such movies are just for entertainment and to make the audience laugh and be happy. However, other kinds of movies like action, thriller, and horror may have a negative impact on society.' (Bashir Memon, Rashid Ali Khuhro, Saman Gul, 2021). Movies can influence society in various ways. Comic, adventure, biographical, and fantasy films typically offer positive effects by entertaining and uplifting audiences. In contrast, action, thriller, and horror movies might have a more negative impact, potentially influencing viewers' emotions and perceptions in a less favorable manner.

➤ Objectives

- To understand the common patterns in film viewing habits of PG students at Shivaji University, Kolhapur.
- To investigate how PG students allocate time slots for watching films within their academic schedules.
- To analyze the correlations between film viewing habits and academic performance.

➤ Scope of Study

The scope of this research on the film viewing habits of postgraduate students at Shivaji University, Kolhapur, encompasses a broad analysis of how students engage with films in the context of their academic, social, and personal lives. This research paper examines the patterns in the selection of films, time management, and the platforms used for viewing, offering insights into the preferences of students regarding genres, formats, and viewing contexts (such as watching alone or in groups). It explores the push and deterrent factors that formed the cinema goers and film

fans with film viewing preferences and behavior amongst the post-graduate students of Shivaji University, Kolhapur. This study will examine how film consumption fits into the students' daily routines amidst academic responsibilities, and how it may affect or reflect their academic performance, mental well-being, and social interactions. Furthermore, the scope includes investigating students' motivations behind watching films—whether for entertainment, relaxation, education, or social commentary—and the role of digital streaming platforms in shaping modern viewing behaviors. Overall, this research seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of how contemporary PG students navigate their film-viewing habits, balancing them with the pressures of academic life, and the evolving digital media landscape.

➤ *Rationale and Significance*

This study aims to explore the film viewing habits of post-graduate students at Shivaji University, Kolhapur, focusing on how these habits intersect with their academic lives. With the growing influence of digital media and diverse streaming platforms, films have become an integral part of student life, offering both entertainment and educational value. Understanding the patterns, preferences, and time management strategies related to film viewing is crucial for grasping how students balance leisure with academic responsibilities. In addition, analyzing the potential correlations between film viewing and academic performance can provide insights into students' cognitive and emotional well-being, time management, and overall media consumption. This research will contribute to the field of mass communication by shedding light on media consumption trends among important demographic, offering valuable information for educators, content creators, and policymakers.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Movies are intended to entertain, but they also provide several mental health benefits for students and the adults who love them. Like adults, students are prone to experiencing feelings of stress, nervousness, and anxiety. A field trip to the cinema with friends or a family movie night at home is a great opportunity to be social and spend time with loved ones. Films can support linguistic skills by introducing children to new vocabulary, its meaning, and pronunciations. One thing that film does very well is its ability to create a sense of immersion and immediacy. Certainly, in war films and documentaries, this is undeniable. Film, however, can also tackle complicated and more subtle issues in ways other media simply can't. It's a powerful construct to explore many social issues and themes deeper and more critically. Examples of topics can include discrimination, equality, morality, and philosophy (Ontario College of teachers, 2020). Movies offer more than just entertainment; they also provide significant mental health benefits for students and adults. Like adults, students often face stress and anxiety, and activities such as cinema trips with friends or family movie nights can be a valuable way to socialize and bond. Films can enhance linguistic skills by exposing viewers to new vocabulary and pronunciations. Additionally, movies create a strong sense of immersion and

immediacy, especially in genres like war films and documentaries. They are capable of addressing complex social issues and themes, such as discrimination, equality, and morality, offering a deeper and more critical exploration of these topics compared to other media.

Many researchers have explored the correlation between movies and listening skills in academic studies. A movie as a learning medium becomes a tool for learning listening skills. This section will discuss students' habits in watching English movies. According to Verplanken (Pratama, 2016), someone's habit is influenced by several factors. Frequency, repetition, and behavior are the three factors to consider. First, frequency counts how many times something happens in a certain amount of time. For example, if someone eats three times a day, his eat frequency is 21 times in a week. Second, repetition; act doing something continuously or repeatedly. Third, behavior; a unique phenomenon characterized by a bodily component's visible and measurable movement over space and time. According to the description above, a habit is a subconscious and continuous pattern of behavior that is repeated until it becomes automatic without conscious thought. In this research, the habit means the students' routine in watching English movies in their daily life. Then, if someone does something repeatedly over a long period, it can be described as a habit. The action is unconsciously and enjoyable (Femalinda Anindita Rachmi, Mariska Intan Sari., 2022). The text explains how students' habits in watching English movies can be understood through three main factors: frequency, repetition, and behavior. Frequency refers to how often students watch these movies, such as daily or weekly. Repetition involves the continuous and regular nature of this activity, which helps in forming a habit. Behavior is about how these watching patterns are observable and measurable. When students watch English movies regularly, it becomes a subconscious routine that feels automatic and enjoyable over time. This habitual watching can help in improving their listening skills in English, as the repetitive exposure aids in language learning. The study shows that students who watch English movies frequently develop a strong and consistent habit. This habitual behavior is marked by regular and repeated viewing, which becomes an automatic part of their daily routines. The research highlights that such repetitive exposure to English through movies significantly enhances students' listening skills, contributing positively to their language acquisition. Additionally, students find watching English movies an enjoyable activity, which further encourages them to integrate it into their routine. The study concludes that this enjoyable and repetitive practice not only improves language comprehension but also helps in making learning more engaging and effective.

Movies are an integral aspect of everyday life, beginning from its inception and growth since 1910, where it evolved from "an industry dominated by mom-and-pop businesses into a mature and complex one" (Fuller 1996). Since then, experts have referred to movies as part of a cinema. However, the cinema itself emerged in the early 19th century, while movies first appeared in the early 20th

century around 1920. During the 20th century, movies began to have many dramatic forms with more innovative photographic depictions (Klarer 1999). There were differences in interpretation to distinguish between cinema and film; is this moving or just an interval? Is it a single image or a series? Is it capturing a place or saving time? Aside from its relationship to other forms of visualization and representation, the question is: Is it science or art? And if the latter, is it uplifting and educational, or distracting and corrupt? These discussions are centered not only on the specifics of cinema, but also on its ontological, epistemological, and anthropological relevance (Elsaesser and Hagener 2015) (Sukadir Kete, Aceng Rahmat, Yumna Rasyid, Ninuk Lustyantje, 2021). The history of cinema has begun very early and the people who watch cinema have a different perception. Many professionals have considered films as part of cinema.

Nowadays films occupy a significant portion of the media products consumed by people. In Russia, cinema is being considered as a means of individual and social transformation, which makes a contribution to the formation of the Russian audience's outlook, including their attitudes towards topical social issues. At the same time, the question of the effectiveness of films' impact remains an open question in psychological science. According to the empirical orientation of our approach to the study of mass media influence, our goal was to obtain new data on the positive impact of films based on specific experimental research. The task was to identify changes in the attitudes of young people, as the most active viewers, towards topical social issues after watching a specifically selected film. Using a psycho semantic technique that included 25 scales designed to identify attitudes towards elderly people, respondents evaluated their various characteristics before and after watching the film. Using a number of characteristics related to the motivational, emotional and cognitive spheres, significant changes were revealed. At the same time, significant differences were found in assessments of the elderly between undergraduate students and postgraduate students. After watching the film, postgraduate students' attitudes towards elderly people changed in a positive way, while undergraduate students' negative assessments only worsened. The revealed opposite trends can be explained by individual differences of respondents, which include age, educational status as an indicator of individual psychological characteristics, the experience of interaction with elderly people and, as a result, attitudes towards elderly people at the time before watching the movie. The finding that previous attitudes mediate the impact of the film complements the ideas of the contribution of individual differences to media effects. Most of the changes detected immediately after watching the movie did not remain over time. A single movie viewing did not have a lasting effect on viewers' attitudes, and it suggests the further task of identifying mechanisms of the sustainability of changes. (Tina, 2020) The varying responses of viewers can be attributed to factors like their age, educational background, personal psychological characteristics, and their prior experiences interacting with elderly individuals. Essentially, viewers' pre-existing differences

shape how they react to the film. A person's educational background might reflect certain psychological traits (e.g., empathy, cognitive maturity) that influence how they interpret the movie and its themes related to elderly people.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

The methodologies employed in research are as diverse as the questions pursued. Quantitative research, wielding the power of numbers and statistical analysis, seeks to uncover patterns, relationships, and causal effects. Surveys, experiments, and intricate statistical models become the tools in this quest for quantifiable understanding. Conversely, qualitative research embraces the richness of human experience, delving into narratives, observations, and in-depth interviews to unravel subjective meanings and explore complex social phenomena. Through careful ethnography and thematic analysis, qualitative researchers paint human-centric portraits of our world.

A research design is defined as the overall plan or structure that guides the process of conducting research. It is a critical component of the research process and serves as a blueprint for how a study will be carried out, including the methods and techniques that will be used to collect and analyze data. A well-designed research study is essential for ensuring that the research objectives are met and that the results are valid and reliable. (Jain, 2023) A strong research design ensures that the study meets its objectives and produces reliable and accurate results. Essentially, it acts as a blueprint, guiding the entire research process to ensure that the findings are meaningful and trustworthy.

The population for my study comprises only postgraduate students from various departments in Shivaji University, Kolhapur. A sample size of 100 is targeted to achieve a comprehensive understanding of the film viewing habits. A stratified random sampling method will be used to ensure representation from different faculties (e.g., Social Science & Humanities, Management & Interdisciplinary studies). The first finding answers the research question about the common film viewing patterns of the PG students in Shivaji University, Kolhapur. The second findings investigate how PG students' allocate time for watching movies while fulfilling their academic commitment. The last finding, which is the third research objective, is to analyze the correlations between film viewing habits and academic performance.

Through Survey a structured questionnaire will be given to the selected sample. My survey will include both closed and open-ended questions to capture quantitative and qualitative data on film viewing habits, preferences, frequency, viewing context, and perceived impact on academic performance. A small interview as per my questionnaire survey will be conducted with 4 students from each faculty to gain deeper insights into personal motivations and the balancing of academic and leisure activities. Each faculty is represented equally, with 25 students from each discipline. This balanced representation aims to capture a diverse range of perspectives on film

viewing habits, ensuring that the findings are reflective of the broader PG student population at the university. An empirical research, involves the collection of original data directly from PG students in Shivaji University. This method is distinct from secondary research, which involves analyzing existing data. Review of existing literature or research papers on film viewing habits, media consumption patterns, and the impact of leisure activities on academic performance will be conducted to support the primary data findings. My secondary data also includes books, journals and website.

➤ *Film Preferences*

Film preferences among postgraduate (PG) students at Shivaji University, Kolhapur, reflect a diverse range of interests shaped by academic disciplines, cultural backgrounds, and social influences. Students from different academic fields may gravitate toward films that resonate with their studies; for instance, literature students might prefer films with strong narratives or adaptations of literary works, while students in social sciences may be drawn to documentaries or films that address societal issues. Cultural backgrounds also play a significant role, as students may favor films in their native languages or those that reflect their heritage and traditions.

Social influences, such as peer groups, popular trends, and access to streaming platforms, shape students' choices as well. Viewing habits may differ based on whether films are watched individually or in groups, as collective viewing often promotes shared experiences and discussions. Additionally, the stress of academic life and tight schedules can also dictate the type of films students prefer—some may choose light-hearted entertainment for relaxation, while others might opt for intellectually stimulating films that align with their academic pursuits. This variety in preferences reflects the complexity and richness of film viewing habits among PG students at Shivaji University.

➤ *Viewing Context*

The film viewing context of postgraduate (PG) students at Shivaji University, Kolhapur, is shaped by a blend of individual preferences, social dynamics, and academic pressures, which collectively influence their film consumption habits. Many students opt for viewing films in group settings, where watching together not only enhances the enjoyment of the experience but also fosters social interactions and discussions about the themes and narratives presented in the films.

Fig 1 (a) Gender Distribution (b) Department Distribution (c) Year of Study (d) Area Distribution

Gender Distribution: Equal representation with 50 males and 50 females. Department Distribution: 25 students from each of the five departments (Social Science, Management, Science, Interdisciplinary, and Arts). Year of

Study: 70% of the students are from the second year, and 30% are from the first year. Area Distribution: Majority (70%) of the students are from rural areas, while 30% are from urban areas.

Fig 2 Preferred Time for Watching Films

In this pie chart, we can see the percentage of PG students' preferred time for watching films; late night – 40%. Evening – 40%, Afternoon – 14%, early morning – 6

%. This table shows that the proportion of late-night movie watchers is high.

Fig 3 Watching Alone or with Others

This pie chart represents how PG students of Shivaji University, Kolhapur watch movies either alone or with others; With friends – 45 %, Alone – 30%, With family –

15%, In a group setting – 10%. Students prefer to watch movies with their friends, according to this chart.

Fig 4 Gender of Films Perferred

The majority of students favored romantic, dramatic, and comedic films, according to this chart. However, a tiny

portion chooses action, documentaries, and horror. Sci-fi is the genre that PG students dislike the most.

Fig 5 How Often do you watch Films?

This pie chart shows how often PG students watch films; Once a week – 50%, 2-3 times a week – 20%, Rarely – 20%, Daily – 10%. The highest percentage of movie watchers in this chart are weekly, while the lowest percentage are daily.

When asked if the film affects your academic performance, 30% of students said it has a positive effect, while 40% said it has no effect. According to 10 percent of students, it has a negative effect, while 20 percent of students did not answer this question. This means that there

are more students who state that there is a positive result and that the result is not.

IV. DISCUSSION

Frequency of Viewing: A significant majority of students (50%) watch films once a week, suggesting that film viewing is a regular yet not overwhelming part of their lives. A smaller percentage watch films daily (10%), while 20% watch 2-3 times a week and 20% watch rarely. This indicates that films are integrated into students' routines but not as a primary activity.

The most favored film genres are comedy, drama, and romance, each preferred by 60% of the respondents. Action films are less popular (20%), while horror, sci-fi, and documentaries each attract only 10-20% of viewers. This preference for lighter genres suggests that students seek entertainment that provides enjoyment and emotional engagement. The predominant platforms for film viewing are Netflix (40%), Hotstar (30%), and YouTube (15%), indicating a strong inclination towards popular streaming services. Amazon Prime is used by 10% of respondents, while 5% use other platforms. This preference highlights the accessibility and convenience of on-demand streaming services. Students generally prefer to watch films with friends (40%), followed by alone (30%). This social aspect of viewing films suggests that film watching serves as a communal activity that fosters social interaction, while solo viewing still maintains a significant role.

The majority prefer to watch films in the evening (40%) or late at night (35%), which indicates that film viewing typically occurs after academic obligations, allowing for relaxation and entertainment. Only 10% watch films early in the morning, and 15% during the afternoon.

Time Management: A considerable number of students (40%) prioritize academics and fit film watching into their free time, while 30% watch films during breaks. This demonstrates a conscious effort to balance academic responsibilities with leisure activities.

About half of the respondents (50%) do not plan their film watching around their academic schedule, reflecting a spontaneous approach to viewing. This might contribute to the overall satisfaction derived from film viewing, as it allows for flexibility. During exam periods or deadlines, 60% of students reduce their film-watching time, with 20% stopping completely. This highlights the prioritization of academic responsibilities during crucial periods.

Film viewing serves as a means of managing stress, with 40% of students believing it helps somewhat, and 35% stating it helps significantly. This suggests that films provide a necessary break from academic pressures.

The data analysis conducted for my research paper has successfully addressed the three primary objectives outlined in the study. Firstly, the analysis sheds light on the common patterns in film viewing habits among postgraduate students at Shivaji University, Kolhapur.

The findings indicate a clear preference for specific genres, with comedy and drama being the most favored, and a notable inclination towards watching films with friends, particularly during evening and late-night hours. For instance, students frequently express that comedy films are their preferred choice during stressful academic periods, as these provide much-needed relief and distraction from academic pressures. However, the struggle to balance film watching with academic responsibilities can lead to feelings of guilt, especially when assignments and deadlines loom large.

Students report that they often find themselves allocating less time to films than they would like, opting for more selective viewing that aligns with their academic interests or provides cultural insights. Additionally, many acknowledge that films have significantly contributed to their personal growth, prompting them to reflect on their identities and beliefs. They appreciate how certain films resonate with their experiences, offering new perspectives that aid in self-discovery. Overall, the transition to postgraduate studies appears to have shifted students' film viewing habits toward a more intentional and reflective approach, where they seek to maximize the positive benefits of films while managing their academic commitments.

The correlation between film viewing habits and academic performance has been effectively analyzed. The results demonstrate that while a significant portion of students feel that film viewing has no detrimental impact on their academic success, many also recognize the potential benefits of watching films in improving focus and relaxation. The data not only highlights the intricate relationship between film viewing and academic life but also emphasizes the importance of maintaining a healthy balance between entertainment and educational responsibilities.

V. CONCLUSION

Film viewing habits offers valuable insights into the broader cultural and social context of PG students, emphasizing the importance of film as a medium for both entertainment and social engagement in their academic lives. The data indicates that films are an essential part of students' lives, serving as both a source of entertainment and a method of stress relief. While students recognize the need to balance their film-viewing habits with academic responsibilities, they generally perceive films as beneficial rather than detrimental to their studies. As the impact of films is long-term, it is not possible to measure it immediately, but films as a medium definitely have an impact on students.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Bashir Memon, Rashid Ali Khuhro, Saman Gul. (2021, July 2). *Movie Watching Preferences and Patterns*. Retrieved August 26, 2024, from ResearchGate: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/353247118_Movie_Watching_Preferences_and_Patterns_A_Survey_of_the_Female_Students_in_the_University_of_Sindh_Jamshoro_Pakistan
- [2]. C.R. Kothari, Gaurav Garg. (2019). *Research Methodology: Methods and Techniques* (4th ed.). New Age International Publishers.
- [3]. Chand, D. S. (2021). *Data Collection: Research Methodology* (Kindle Edition ed.). Kindle
- [4]. Creswell, J. W. (2009). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches* (3rd ed., Vol. 3). Sage Publication.

- [5]. Femalinda Anindita Rachmi, Mariska Intan Sari. (2022). Students' Habit in Watching English Movies and Its Correlation. *academia* , 19.
- [6]. Jain, N. (2023, september 8). A research design is defined as the overall plan or structure that guides the process of conducting research. It is a critical component of the research process and serves as a blueprint for how a study will be carried out, including the methods and techn. Retrieved September 19, 2024, from Idea scale: <https://ideascale.com/blog/what-is-research-design/>
- [7]. Kabir, S. M. (2016). *INTRODUCTION TO RESEARCH* (1st ed.). Book Zone publication
- [8]. Kubrak, T. (2020). Impact of Films: Changes in Young People's Attitudes after Watching a Movie. *MDPI* , 10.
- [9]. Mark P. McElreath &John M. Blamphin. (1994). Partial Answers to Priority Research Questions—and Gaps—Found in the Public Relations Society of America's Body of Knowledge. *Journal of Public Relations Research* , 6 (2), 69-103.
- [10]. Ontario College of teachers. (2024). *The TOC Blog*. Toronto: Ontario College.
- [11]. Portal, S. G. (2020). *STACK* . Retrieved from <https://www.developer.tech.gov.sg/communities/events/conferences/stack-2020/overview.html>
- [12]. Robert E.L. Faris, William Form. (2024, september 12). *data collection*. Retrieved september 19, 2024, from [britannica: https://www.britannica.com/topic/sociology/Data-collection](https://www.britannica.com/topic/sociology/Data-collection)
- [13]. Shendurnikar, N. (2013). Exploring Interdisciplinarity in Indian Media Education and Research: An Analysis. *Adademia* (https://www.academia.edu/4690194/Exploring_Interdisciplinarity_in_Indian_Media_Education_and_Research_An_Analysis).
- [14]. Sukadir Kete, Aceng Rahmat, Yumna Rasyid, Ninuk Lustyantie. (2021). The Effect of Movie-watching Habits and Creative Thinking Abilities on. *Richtmann* , 11.
- [15]. Testbook. (2023). *Major Theoretical Strands of Research Methodology in Sociology*. Retrieved January 27, 2024, from <https://testbook.com/ias-preparation/major-theoretical-strands-of-research-methodology>